

1 **Bioavailability of phenolics from an oleuropein-rich olive (*Olea europaea*) leaf extract and its acute effect**
2 **on plasma antioxidant status. Comparison between pre- and postmenopausal women**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 **Purpose:** Preclinical studies suggest a potential protective effect of oleuropein in osteoporosis and one of the
3 proposed mechanisms is the modulation of the oxidative stress. Oleuropein bioavailability and its effect on
4 antioxidant status in pre- and postmenopausal women are unknown. The aim of the present study was to
5 investigate the oral bioavailability of an olive leaf extract rich in oleuropein (40 %) and its effect on antioxidant
6 status in postmenopausal women compared to premenopausal women. **Methods:** premenopausal (n=8) and
7 postmenopausal women (n=8) received 250 mg of olive leaf extract and blood samples (t=0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12,
8 16 and 24h) were taken and 24h urine divided in five fractions were collected. Olive leaf extract derived
9 metabolites were analyzed in plasma and urine by HPLC-ESI-QTOF and UPLC-ESI-QqQ, and
10 pharmacokinetics parameters were determined. Ferric reducing antioxidant ability (FRAP) and malondialdehyde
11 (MDA) levels were measured in plasma. **Results:** Plasma levels of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol
12 sulfate, oleuropein aglycon glucuronide and oleuropein aglycon derivative 1 were higher in postmenopausal
13 women. MDA levels were significantly decreased (32 %) in postmenopausal women and inversely correlated
14 with hydroxytyrosol sulfate levels. Postmenopausal women excreted less sulfated metabolites than
15 premenopausal women in urine. **Conclusions:** Our results suggest that postmenopausal women could be a target
16 population for the intake of olive phenolics in order to prevent age-related and oxidative stress-related processes
17 such as osteoporosis.

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19 **Keywords:** Malondialdehyde, oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, pharmacokinetics, bioavailability,
20 postmenopausal, antioxidant.

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1 1. Introduction

2 One of the most important and characteristic components of the Mediterranean diet is olive oil, to which many of
3 the health promoting effects of the Mediterranean diet are attributed. The beneficial effects of olive oil
4 consumption appear to be due in part to the phenolic fraction present in the olive oil [1]. While the olive fruits
5 are typically used for human consumption, olive leaves are also a rich source of the same type of phenolic
6 compounds: oleuropeosides, flavones, flavonols, flavan-3-ols, and substituted phenolics such as hydroxytyrosol
7 and tyrosol. Among them, oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol are the most abundant phenolic compounds found in
8 olive leaves [2]. Human, animal and *in vitro* studies have demonstrated the beneficial effect of olive oil
9 phenolics in several chronic diseases [1]. The biological effects of a compound are related, in some manner, to
10 the time course of the concentration of the administered compound or its active metabolite in the blood stream
11 [3]. Therefore, bioavailability studies are key points in clinical studies and critical to establish the effect of a
12 compound or set of compounds in the body [4]. Drug bioavailability is influenced by several factors like
13 administration route, genetic phenotype, age, gender, food interaction and feeding condition [5]. Studies dealing
14 with the influence of these factors on phenolics bioavailability are scarce but previous studies indicate an
15 influence of food matrix, age, sex and hormonal status [6, 7]. Recently, a gender effect has been described in
16 oleuropein leaf extract metabolism [8] but studies focused on the bioavailability of these compounds in
17 premenopausal and postmenopausal women have not been conducted so far. Most of the studies dealing with the
18 bioavailability of olive phenolics have been carried out with olive oil, with hydroxytyrosol as the most
19 frequently studied phenolic [9-11] Furthermore, oleuropein content decreases in the green maturation phase of
20 the olive fruit and oleuropein levels in olive oils are low [12], thus data about its bioavailability are scarce.

21 Oxidative stress is one of the main factors associated to age-related pathologies like cancer,
22 cardiovascular diseases, neurological diseases and osteoporosis [13, 14]. In postmenopausal women, accelerated
23 bone loss that occurs following lack of estrogens can be correlated to an increase in cytokine production by
24 peripheral blood monocytes concomitant with reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation [15]. In fact,
25 osteoporotic women have low antioxidant levels and the antioxidant deficiency has a negative impact on bone
26 mass [16]. Recent studies demonstrated that oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol were able to enhance the deposition
27 of calcium ions in osteoblastic MC3T3-E1 cells and to inhibit osteoclast formation. Furthermore, in
28 ovariectomized rats, an experimental model of postmenopausal osteoporosis, the oral administration of
29 oleuropein and particularly hydroxytyrosol reduced the loss of trabecular bone [17]. Similarly, oral tyrosol and
30 hydroxytyrosol prevented inflammation-induced osteopenia in ovariectomized rats and diet supplementation

1 with hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol and oleuropein prevented inflammation-induced bone loss [18, 19]. In elderly men,
2 at high cardiovascular risk, the consumption of a Mediterranean diet rich in olive oil for two years increased
3 markedly the osteocalcin and procollagen I N-terminal propeptide levels [20]. Furthermore, *ex vivo* studies have
4 been performed in which the effect of oleuropein was investigated on the differentiation of mesenchymal stem
5 cells (MSCs) isolated from human bone marrow, which are the progenitor cells for both osteoblasts and
6 adipocytes. In these studies, it was demonstrated that oleuropein was able to inhibit the differentiation of these
7 MSCs into adipocytes, and to enhance differentiation into osteoblasts [21]. One hypothesis of the mechanism of
8 action of olive phenolics is the suppression of oxidative stress, as some of the processes in which an effect of
9 olive phenolics have been described i.e. alkaline phosphatase activity, expression of collagen type I and
10 mineralization of osteoblastic cells are processes in which oxidative stress is involved [22-24].

11 All the above suggests that postmenopausal women could be a target population for the administration of
12 olive phenolics for osteoporosis prevention, on account of the lower levels of antioxidant defenses in
13 postmenopausal women and the preclinical evidence suggesting a possible role of olive phenolics in the
14 prevention of osteoporosis [16-19]. In order to provide further insights on this hypothesis, our aim was i) to
15 evaluate the plasma antioxidant status of pre- and postmenopausal women upon oral intake of an oleuropein-rich
16 olive leaf extract, and ii) to study the pharmacokinetics and urine excretion of olive phenolics in both groups of
17 women to establish a possible correlation between antioxidant effects and bioavailability of olive phenolics.

18 **2. Material and methods**

19 2.1 Reagents

20 Hydroxytyrosol glucuronide was synthesized according to Lucas et al. [25]. Gallic acid, 2,4-
21 dinitrophenylhydrazine and tetraethoxypropane were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).
22 Methanol and formic acid were supplied from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) and acetonitrile from Romil
23 (Barcelona, Spain). Water was deionized by using a Milli-Q-system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA).
24 BONOLIVE[®], consisting of an optimized mixture of polyphenols derived from olive leaf, standardized for its
25 oleuropein content (>40%), was supplied by BioActor (Maastricht, The Netherlands). BONOLIVE[®] is
26 manufactured in accordance with food grade and food safety standards embraced by the Global Food Safety
27 Initiative (FSSC 22000).

28 2.2 Subjects

29 Women, aged between 18 and 75 years, were recruited from the volunteer database of the Drug Research Unit of
30 Maastricht (The Netherlands), by e-mail and by advertisements. A physical examination including a general

1 physical examination, vital signs (blood pressure, heart rate, body temperature and respiratory rate), body height
2 and weight and blood sampling for liver and renal function were performed. In premenopausal subjects a
3 pregnancy test was performed using a urine portion. In premenopausal women no history of hormone-related
4 disorders or surgical interventions affecting female hormone balance (e.g. ovariectomy) was allowed.
5 Premenopausal women had to be on monophasic oral anti-conception and the test day could not be in the pause
6 week or first three days of pill use, in order to obtain a constant level of estrogen. To ensure a homogeneous
7 population postmenopausal women had to be at least two years postmenopausal. The subjects were not allowed
8 to use hormones, medicinal products, food supplements, anti-osteoporosis medication or vitamins. Exclusion
9 criteria for study participation were: smokers, clinically significant abnormal liver functioning, clinically
10 significant abnormal serum creatinine, an abnormal body mass index (BMI) (below 18 or above 30), the use of
11 concomitant medications or supplements, and having blood donated during the last 4 weeks. Screening
12 continued until twenty (two groups of ten) eligible volunteers were selected. From each study group, eight
13 individuals started the study. The other two acted as backup for potential drop-outs.

14 2.3 Study design and sample collection

15 The study was a parallel trial carried out in the Drug Research Unit of Maastricht (The Netherlands) according to
16 the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and its amendments. The design was approved by the
17 Medical Ethical Committee of the University Hospital Maastricht. All participants gave their express consent to
18 participate in the study. The two study groups consisted of eight healthy premenopausal and eight healthy
19 postmenopausal women who were 19-25 and 51-66 years old respectively. Mean body mass index (BMI) was
20 22.7 kg/m² for premenopausal and 23.8 kg/m² for postmenopausal women. Blood pressure was in the normal
21 range. Serum creatinine, hematocrit, aspartate transaminase and alanine transaminase values were normal.
22 Baseline characteristics are shown in supplemental Table 1. Women were invited to the clinical facility at 7:30
23 AM. They were asked not to consume food products or beverages (except for water) from midnight of the day
24 before arriving to the facility. For the pre-dose blood sampling and sampling after the treatment, a venous
25 catheter was placed in the arm of each subject. The baseline blood sample was collected within two hours before
26 intake of the olive leaf extract (t=0). Participants were asked to urinate just before intake of the supplement. The
27 olive leaf extract was provided in the form of hard gelatin capsules, containing 250 mg of the extract. Subjects
28 were instructed to orally ingest one capsule with 200 mL of water within one minute. Subsequently blood
29 samples were drawn ten times at 30 min, 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h, 6h, 8h, 12h, 16h and 24h. The samples were temporarily
30 stored in a cooled dark box and centrifuged as soon as possible upon collection (1300xg, 10 minutes, 4 °C). The

1 plasma collected was immediately acidified using 36 μL HCl/mL plasma (4 M) at pH 3.0. Urine samples were
2 collected and pooled as follows: 0-4h, 4-8h, 8-12h, 12-16h and 16-24h. During this period of collection, the
3 urine samples were stored in the fridge. After each collection, butyl-hydroxytoluene was added as an antioxidant
4 at a final concentration of 40 μM . The volunteers received a snack, standard lunch, dinner and second snack after
5 2h, 4h, 9h and 13h respectively. At the end of the study day, vital signs were measured again, and subjects were
6 asked whether they had experienced adverse events.

7 2.4 Analysis of the olive leaf extract

8 A sample of 40 mg olive leaf extract was extracted with 2 mL of methanol:water (50:50). The mixture was
9 vortexed, subjected to ultrasonic bath for 5 minutes, and centrifuged at 15000xg for 10 min. The supernatants
10 were filtered through a 0.45 μm PVDF filter and a sample of 20 μL was directly injected into the HPLC-DAD
11 MS/MS system.

12 2.5 Extraction procedures for plasma and urine samples

13 Plasma samples were thawed and 200 μL were extracted with 600 μL acetonitrile: formic acid (99.8: 0.2, v/v) by
14 vortexing for 2 min and ultrasonic bath for 10 min. The mixture was centrifuged at 19000xg for 10 min and the
15 supernatant was reduced to dryness in a speed vacuum concentrator. The dried samples were re-suspended in
16 200 μL of MeOH:H₂O (1:1, v/v) plus 0.1% formic acid and filter before analysis by HPLC. Urine samples were
17 thawed, vortexed, centrifuged at 19000xg for 10 min, filtered through a 0.45 μm PVDF filter and diluted 1:5
18 with water plus 0.1% formic acid. Prior to the injection, 0.2 ppm of internal standard (gallic acid) was added to
19 urine and plasma samples.

20 2.6 HPLC-ESI-QTOF and UPLC-ESI-QqQ

21 The qualitative analysis was developed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity LC system coupled to the 6550 Accurate-
22 Mass Quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) using an electrospray
23 interface (Jet Stream Technology). Compounds were separated on a reverse phase Poroshell 120 EC-C18 column
24 (3 x 100 mm, 2.7 μm) (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) operating at 30 °C and a flow rate of 0.4
25 mL/min. The mobile phases used were water with 0.1% formic acid (Phase A) and acetonitrile with 0.1% formic
26 acid (Phase B) and the solvent gradient change according to the following conditions: 0-10 min, 1-18% B; 10-16
27 min, 18-38%; 16-19 min, 38-95%. Finally, the B content was decreased to the initial conditions (1%) in 1 min
28 and the column re-equilibrated for 5 min. The optimal conditions of the electrospray interface were as follows:
29 gas temperature 280 °C, drying gas 9 L/min, nebulizer 35 psi, sheath gas temperature 400 °C, sheath gas flow 12
30 L/min. Spectra were acquired in the range 100-1100 m/z in negative mode and fragmentor voltage was 100 V.

1 Data were processed using MassHunter Qualitative Analysis software. Quantitative analysis was carried out
2 using an Agilent Technologies 1290 infinity chromatograph coupled to a 6460 Triple Quadrupole (QQQ) mass
3 spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an interface Jet Stream ESI source
4 operating in negative ion mode. Chromatographic and electrospray conditions were the same used in the analysis
5 with QTOF. All compounds were monitored in the multiple reaction monitoring mode (MRM) using two or
6 three transitions for each compound: a quantifier and at least one qualifier. Fragmentor voltage and collision
7 energy for each transition were optimized.

8 To get an exact quantification of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, a reference standard was chemically synthesized.
9 As such reference standards were not available for other metabolites, data of the other compounds are expressed
10 as areas of intensity (AOI) of the corresponding ion (Area standards/Area internal standard). The hydroxytyrosol
11 glucuronide concentration in urine and plasma was determined by interpolation in the calibration curve obtained
12 with the synthesized standard. Preliminary studies of matrix effect were developed comparing the slopes of
13 calibration curves in solvent (water with 0.1% formic acid) and in the post-extraction spiked sample (urine and
14 plasma). No significant differences in standard response in solvent and in matrix were observed (data not
15 shown). Good linearity was achieved in the range LOQ-20 μM with significant correlation ($R^2 \geq 0.9997$). The
16 limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were obtained by injecting successively diluted standard
17 solutions and were calculated according to the IUPAC method based on a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3 for the
18 LOD and of 10 for the LOQ. The results showed LODs of 0.015 μM (4.95 ppb) and LOQs of 0.050 μM (16.5
19 ppb). The recovery of the compounds during sample preparation was calculated using control samples of plasma
20 spiked with the standard solution of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide at three final concentrations (0.5 μM , 2 μM and
21 10 μM). The recovery percentages expressed as an average of the different concentrations were 78.7 ± 3.19 %.
22 Repeatability was evaluated by injecting control samples spiked with 5 μM of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide five
23 times in the same day (intra-day repeatability) and in five different days (inter-day repeatability). The results
24 expressed as the relative standard deviation (RSD) of peak areas were 4.5 % for intra-day repeatability and 6.3 %
25 for inter-day repeatability.

26 2.7 Pharmacokinetic analysis

27 Plasma and urine concentration–time data of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide and area of intensity (AOI)-time data
28 of the main metabolites were analyzed by non-compartmental pharmacokinetic analysis. Pharmacokinetic
29 parameters were estimated using the WinNonlin software package (version 6.3., Pharsight Corp., Paris, France)
30 model 200-202. The area under the concentration-time curve (AUC) from the time of dosing to the time of the

1 last observation, regardless of whether the last concentration is measurable or not (AUC_{last}) was estimated using
2 the Linear Trapezoidal with Logarithmic Interpolation calculation method. AUC was extrapolated to infinity
3 (AUC_∞) by dividing the last measured concentration by the terminal elimination rate constant (λ_z). Maximum
4 plasma concentration (C_{max}), the lag time (T_{lag}), defined as the time prior to the first measurable (nonzero)
5 concentration, and time to maximum concentration (T_{max}) were determined in the concentration versus time
6 curve. Other calculated pharmacokinetics parameters were the mean residence time (MRT_{last}), which is defined
7 as the average time for a molecule to reside in the body calculated from the time of dosing to the time of the last
8 measurable concentration, the mean residence time calculated using trapezoid area calculations extrapolated to
9 infinity (MRT_∞) and the elimination half-life (T_{1/2}) that is calculated by the formula $T_{1/2} = \ln 2 / \lambda_z$.

10 2.8 Ferric-reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) method and malondialdehyde (MDA) analysis

11 FRAP method was assayed in plasma as described by Larrosa et al. [26]. An aliquot of 10 μ L of plasma was
12 added to 190 μ L of the FRAP reagent, and the absorbance at 593 nm was monitored for 45 min in a plate reader
13 (Infinite M200 Tecan, Grodig, Austria). A standard curve was determined with FeCl₂ and results were expressed
14 as μ M Fe²⁺/mL of plasma. The concentration of total (free and protein-bound) plasma MDA was determined by
15 HPLC according to the method developed by Mateos et al. [27]. A sample aliquot of 80 μ L was injected onto an
16 Agilent 1100 HPLC-DAD with a Lichrocart C18 column (4.0 mm \times 125 mm, 5- μ m particle size, Agilent) and
17 isocratically eluted with 1% (v/v) acetic acid in deionized water, and acetonitrile (62:38, v/v) at a flow rate of 0.6
18 mL/min. The MDA-TBA adduct was detected at 310 nm. For quantification the intensities of the MDA-TBA
19 peak areas were compared to standards produced by the acidic hydrolysis of tetraethoxypropane (Sigma, St.
20 Louis, MO, USA).

21 2.9 Statistics

22 The data were analyzed using the SPSS Software, version 21.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) Data are
23 presented as the mean \pm SD except for the T_{1/2} pharmacokinetic parameter which data is presented as the
24 harmonic mean \pm SD. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test agreement of the empirical distribution of the data
25 with normality assumption. Statistical significance for normal data was determined by unpaired or paired
26 Student's t test, using two-tailed and P<0.05 as the level of significance. When normal distribution could not be
27 assumed the nonparametric Wilcoxon signed rank test or the Mann Whitney test were used to compare data.
28 Bivariate correlations were used to quantify associations between variables.

29 3. Results

30 3.1 Subjects characteristics

1 All women completed the study and none experienced adverse effects (intolerance, nausea, dyspepsia,
2 constipation, diarrhea, allergic reactions, etc.) regarding the intake of the supplied product. There was overall
3 compliance for blood sampling, the collection of 24-hour urine and adherence to the treatment. Test subject
4 characteristics and serobiochemical parameters at inclusion (Supplemental Table 1) and after the intervention
5 (data not shown) did not differ among groups with the exception of diastolic pressure and temperature that were
6 different at both times.

7 3.2 Qualitative analysis of olive leaf extract

8 Fifteen compounds were identified in the olive leaf extract (Table 1, Supplemental Figure 1), most of them in
9 glycosylated form. The most abundant polyphenol was oleuropein of which three different isomers were found at
10 different retention times but with the same molecular weight and mass spectrometric daughter ions. Other
11 oleuropein derivatives found were oleoside, dimethyl-oleuropein and hydroxy-oleuropein and a low quantity of
12 hydroxytyrosol glucoside and elenolic acid glucoside.

13 3.3 Plasma and urine metabolites

14 After ingestion of 250 mg olive leaf extract, metabolites were all identified using accurate mass in full scan MS
15 and MS/MS mode. Accurate mass leads to the chemical formula and MS/MS analysis provides valuable
16 information about fragmentation pattern. In a targeted analysis, a total of 47 metabolites that could derive from
17 the intake of olive leaf extract were searched for. Explored metabolites in plasma and urine samples were mainly
18 Phase II-derived metabolites (methylated, sulfated and glucuronidated metabolites) of hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol,
19 oleuropein aglycon, ligstroside aglycon, elenolic acid, decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon, luteolin and
20 apigenin. In plasma and urine at baseline (t=0), no olive phenolic-related metabolites were found. None of the
21 parent compounds present in the olive leaf extract were found in the plasma or urine and most of the metabolites
22 appeared in conjugated form, mainly glucuronidated and sulfated. The main metabolites found in plasma were
23 three metabolites derived from hydroxytyrosol, four oleuropein aglycon derivatives and two homovanillic acid
24 metabolites whereas tyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol acetate glucuronide and luteolin glucuronide and its
25 respective aglycone were found at trace levels. The list of metabolites tentatively identified in plasma and urine
26 is shown in Table 2. The urinary metabolite profile was very similar to that found in plasma with the exception
27 of homovanillic alcohol sulfate, elenoic acid and elenoic glucuronide that appeared exclusively in urine whereas
28 no traces of luteolin, previously detected in plasma, were found in urine.

29 Standards and samples where these metabolites were previously detected were used to optimize their transitions:
30 product ions, collision energy and fragmentor. Supplemental Table 2 summarizes the optimized MRM

1 conditions for each compound quantified. Chemically synthesized standard of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide was
2 used for the optimization and accurate quantification of this compound in plasma and urine. For the other
3 metabolites with not available standards the results of quantification were expressed as areas of intensity (AOI)
4 of the corresponding ion (Area standards/Area internal standard). These data are relative and can help to
5 understand the pharmacokinetic behavior of each metabolite and to compare the same metabolite among
6 volunteers. However, they do not allow exact quantification of the metabolites.

7 3.4 Plasma and urine pharmacokinetic analysis

8 The absorption-time profiles in plasma and excretion-time profiles in urine for each metabolite are shown in
9 Figures 1 and 2, respectively. As can be observed the absorption pattern of the different phenolic compounds in
10 plasma was very similar in both premenopausal and postmenopausal women (Fig. 1). The same occurred with
11 the urine excretion-time profiles where the maximum excretion rate for all the compounds was reached in the
12 first fraction, between 0 and 4 hours after the intake (Fig. 2). All detected metabolites appeared rapidly in
13 plasma, as indicated by the Tlag parameter that was 0 for the majority of the volunteers, reaching the maximum
14 peak concentration (Cmax) within the first 35-75 min (Tmax) (Table 4). In both groups, the first metabolite that
15 reached the maximum peak concentration was hydroxytyrosol glucuronide whereas hydroxytyrosol sulfate was
16 the last one (Table 4). There were no differences in Tlag or Tmax parameters among women groups. Plasma
17 maximum concentrations (Cmax) of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol sulfate, oleuropein aglycon
18 glucuronide and oleuropein aglycon derivative 1 (m/z at 571) were significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in
19 postmenopausal women compared with the premenopausal women (Table 4; Fig 1). These higher Cmax values
20 corresponded with significantly higher AUCall values for the mentioned metabolites (Table 4). When the area
21 under the time-concentration curve was extrapolated to infinity (AUC_{∞}) significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were
22 observed for hydroxytyrosol sulfate and oleuropein aglycon glucuronide. A trend, but not significant difference
23 for hydroxytyrosol glucuronide ($P = 0.074$) and oleuropein aglycon derivative 1 ($P = 0.058$) was also observed,
24 whereas no significant differences in MRT or half-life ($T_{1/2}$) pharmacokinetics parameters were found (Table 4).
25 Plasma pharmacokinetic parameters of hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide and homovanillic alcohol glucuronide
26 did not differ between premenopausal and postmenopausal woman (Table 4). Regarding urine, all metabolites
27 that were found in plasma were also identified in urine. In addition, new metabolites derived from oleuropein
28 were identified in urine, i.e. homovanillic alcohol sulfate, elenolic acid and elenolic acid glucuronide. No
29 significant differences were found among metabolites in the parameter Tmax Rate. The total excretion of
30 hydroxytyrosol sulfate and hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide was significantly higher in premenopausal women

1 than in postmenopausal women (Table 5, Fig 2). A similar trend was observed for the oleuropein aglycon
2 derivative 1 with m/z at 571 that became significant ($P=0.023$) in the parameter AUC_{∞} (Table 5).

3 3.5 Statistical associations

4 Bivariate correlation analyses were performed to quantify association between pharmacokinetic parameters in
5 plasma, urine and plasma-urine metabolites. In plasma, there was an association between the AUC_{Call} of
6 hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol sulfate and oleuropein aglycon glucuronide ($r=0.774$, $P=0.000$;
7 $r=0.886$, $P=0.000$) whereas the AUC of hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide was positively correlated with the AUC
8 of homovanillic acid ($r=0.670$, $P=0.005$). Regarding urine, in general, there was a high association between the
9 AUC_{Call} of all metabolites in urine with the exception of hydroxytyrosol sulfate, i.e. the AUC_{Call} of
10 hydroxytyrosol glucuronide in urine was positively correlated with the AUC_{Rall} of hydroxytyrosol
11 sulfoglucuronide ($r=0.698$, $P=0.03$), homovanillic alcohol glucuronide ($r=0.877$, $P=0.000$), oleuropein aglycon
12 glucuronide ($r=0.689$, $P=0.04$) and the oleuropein aglycon derivative 1 571 ($r=0.776$, $P=0.01$).

13 Bivariate correlation analysis between plasma and urinary metabolites showed no association among AUC_{Call} ,
14 AUC_{∞} and C_{max} plasma pharmacokinetic parameters and AUR_{Call} , AUR_{∞} and total amount excreted of
15 urine metabolites with the exception of hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide. Total amount of hydroxytyrosol
16 sulfoglucuronide recovered in urine, AUR_{Call} and AUR_{∞} were positively correlated with AUC_{Call} , AUC_{∞} and
17 C_{max} of hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide in plasma ($p<0.05$). Moreover, the AUC_{Call} of hydroxytyrosol
18 sulfoglucuronide in plasma was correlated with the AUR_{Call} of hydroxytyrosol sulfate in urine ($r=0.642$,
19 $P=0.007$). When bivariate analyses were performed independently for premenopausal and postmenopausal
20 women the mentioned correlations were maintained and no significant differences were found between
21 premenopausal and postmenopausal women.

22 3.5 Ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) and malondialdehyde levels

23 No significant differences were found between premenopausal and postmenopausal women groups in the ferric
24 reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) and plasma malondialdehyde levels (MDA) at the inclusion in the study. No
25 significant changes were found in FRAP plasma levels in pre- or postmenopausal women at thirty minutes, one
26 and two hours after the ingestion of the oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract (results not shown). MDA value
27 decreased (13.8%), although not significantly, in the premenopausal group at 30 min, whereas MDA content was
28 significantly lower at that time (32%, $P=0.016$) in the postmenopausal group. Bivariate correlation analyses
29 between MDA plasma levels and the levels of different metabolites showed no significant association.

30 4. Discussion

1 Phenolics from *Olea europaea* have been reported to exert a number of biological effects [1]. Despite
2 the huge output of results dealing with the antioxidant activity of olive phenolics, the direct correlation between
3 circulating metabolites and plasmatic antioxidant status has been scarcely studied. Furthermore, the antioxidant
4 activity of their conjugated metabolites has not been addressed thoroughly and whether the phenolic conjugated
5 forms are the responsible of the biological effects attributed to phenolic consumption is still an unresolved
6 question. In fact, hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, one of the main metabolites found in plasma after olive phenolics
7 consumption, did not show any antiradical effect in comparison with its parent compound hydroxytyrosol, and
8 only maintained a slight activity protecting LDL-from Cu-mediated oxidation [28]. Furthermore, hormonal
9 status and/or age could influence phenolics bioavailability [7]. These are key points to take into account when
10 the effect of phenolic compounds is studied in diseases in which age, oxidative stress and hormonal status are
11 associated, for example, among others, osteoporosis [14]. Considering this background, we carried out a
12 pharmacokinetic study in order to determine the influence of hormonal status and/or age on the bioavailability of
13 olive leaf phenolics and to correlate the presence of various plasma metabolites with the plasma antioxidant
14 status in pre- and postmenopausal women.

15 Previous studies have reported a high stability of oleuropein in gastric juice and duodenal fluid *in vitro*
16 as well as its low uptake in an isolated perfused rat intestine model, which suggested that oleuropein was poorly
17 absorbed [11, 29, 30]. However, in a successive human study with ileostomy subjects an absorption of this
18 compound is described although oleuropein aglycone or oleuropein were not measured, and plasma was not
19 explored [11]. Further studies in rats confirmed that oleuropein and its hydrolysis derived metabolite
20 hydroxytyrosol were present in plasma, feces and urine as such and also conjugated as glucuronide after oral
21 oleuropein administration [31-33]. Recently, two studies have addressed thoroughly the bioavailability of
22 phenolics from olive oil -derived in humans [34, 35]. García-Villalba et al. tentatively identified 60 metabolites
23 in urine, with oleuropein aglycon and ligstroside aglycon derivatives as the most abundant ones. This suggested
24 that oleuropein and ligstroside were absorbed and subjected to Phase II metabolism in humans. Suarez et al.
25 identified 24 phenolic-derived metabolites in plasma after the administration of a phenol-enriched olive oil, and
26 identified the presence of oleuropein aglycone and its glucuronidated form, which also confirmed that oleuropein
27 was absorbed and metabolized [35]. In the present study, we have detected fifteen metabolites in plasma, with
28 hydroxytyrosol glucuronide as the most abundant one, in contrast to the results of Suarez et al. who did not
29 detected hydroxytyrosol glucuronide in plasma and in agreement with those of de Bock et al. who found
30 hydroxytyrosol conjugates as main derived metabolites after oleuropein-rich leaf extract intake [8]. We have also

1 identified for the first time the presence of hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide in human plasma. Our results
2 support that secoiridoid derivatives are hydrolyzed in the upper gastrointestinal tract [11, 35], as hydroxytyrosol
3 glucuronide appeared rapidly in plasma (in the first 30 min after olive leaf extract intake). In agreement with
4 Suarez et al., [35] the hydrolysis of oleuropein into hydroxytyrosol and elenolic acid was not complete as
5 oleuropein aglycon glucuronide and other derivatives were also detected in the plasma. The high correlation
6 found in plasma among hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol sulfate and oleuropein aglycon glucuronide
7 metabolites could be indicative of a greater or lesser efficiency of gastric hydrolysis in each individual.

8 The absorption pattern of the different phenolic compounds in plasma was very similar. The underlying
9 absorption mechanisms for olive phenolics are not clear and different hypotheses have been raised for the
10 different classes of phenolic compounds. Passive diffusion and transcellular, paracellular or via a glucose
11 transporter have been proposed for hydroxytyrosol and oleuropein respectively [36, 29]. In agreement with
12 previous results [34, 37] urine excretion kinetics were similar for the majority of compounds. Maximum urine
13 excretion rate was reached in the first four hours and then a fast decrease toward basal levels was observed with
14 the exception of the sulfated metabolites, whose excretion was not complete at 24 h after the intake of olive leaf
15 extract. The excretion profiles in urine of the sulfated compounds could be related to their enterohepatic
16 circulation. This pattern of excretion for the sulfated metabolites is reported here for the first time since García-
17 Villalba et al. only analyzed urine fractions within the first 6h after olive oil ingestion [34]. Bivariate analyses
18 between plasma and urine metabolites showed a general lack of correlation between plasma and urine
19 metabolites levels. This could be explained because once the olive phenolics are ingested and absorbed they are
20 widely distributed in multiple organs (i.e. liver, kidney, brain, spleen) or further metabolized [11, 38]. In fact, we
21 detected urine metabolites that were not previously detected in plasma (homovanillic alcohol sulfate, elenolic
22 acid and elenolic acid glucuronide). Unfortunately, the absence of pure standards prevented the calculation of a
23 mass balance between the amounts of ingested phenolics, circulating plasma metabolites and those excreted in
24 urine.

25 In our study, pharmacokinetic analyses of plasma metabolites revealed that the absorption of
26 hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol sulfate and oleuropein aglycon glucuronide was higher in
27 postmenopausal than in premenopausal women whereas in the urine only hydroxytyrosol sulfate excretion was
28 significantly different. Little is known about the effect of age and/or menopause status in polyphenol absorption.
29 A negative correlation between estradiol levels and phytoestrogen exposure has been suggested in women with
30 the PvuII ESR1 polymorphism for the estrogen receptor [39]. Cassidy et al. [7] found a 20% of increase in

1 daidzein bioavailability in postmenopausal women in comparison with premenopausal women suggesting that
2 the observed trend to higher $T_{1/2}$ elimination rates in postmenopausal women could be explained at least in part
3 by the different AUC values between premenopausal and postmenopausal women. However, Faughnan et al.
4 found similar urine excretion of daidzein independently of the age or hormonal status [40]. In our study
5 significant different $T_{1/2}$ values were found between premenopausal and postmenopausal women only for
6 oleuropein aglycon glucuronide. A possible explanation for our results could be the change in the physiological
7 conditions in the stomach that occurs with age. There is a decrease in gastric emptying with age [41] that could
8 favor the oleuropein hydrolysis. On the other hand, the excreted amount of sulfated compounds in urine was
9 higher in premenopausal than in postmenopausal women. It is known that age can affect the expression of Phase
10 II enzymes. In animal studies, the downregulation of gene expression related to Phase II enzymes has been
11 reported in older animals [42, 43]. Another study also reported a decrease in the glucuronidation of the flavonoid
12 genistein in older rats [44]. Overall, these results support the higher amount of sulfated metabolites in the urine
13 of premenopausal women in our study. Nevertheless, apart from the obvious high correlation between hormonal
14 status and age, a direct effect of the different hormonal status of the two women groups cannot be discarded as
15 the regulation of some sulfotransferases such as the estrogen sulfotransferase regulated by the luteinizing
16 hormone has been reported [45].

17 In order to establish whether the different bioavailability of some metabolites was related to the
18 antioxidant status of plasma, we next evaluated FRAP and MDA plasma levels. Previously Kountouri et al.
19 described a significant correlation between total polyphenolic compounds and total plasma antioxidant status 4h
20 after olives consumption, despite the fact that the plasma concentration of polyphenol compounds at 4h was very
21 similar to that of control subjects, and no relationships were found between individual phenolic compounds and
22 total plasma antioxidant activity [37]. In our study, FRAP levels were only determined until 2h after olive leaf
23 extract ingestion because volunteers consumed food after this time point which could interfere with plasma
24 antioxidant status [46]. MDA levels did not correlate with any of the metabolites in plasma. It would have been
25 of great interest to study the correlation between total plasma metabolites and MDA levels as previously was
26 described by Kountouri and coworkers [37]. However, we could not quantify the metabolites due to the lack of
27 available standards and areas of intensity (AOI) cannot be added. The quantified hydroxytyrosol glucuronide
28 levels did not correlated with the MDA levels in agreement with Khymenets et al. [28] who reported that
29 hydroxytyrosol glucuronide (5-10 μ M) exerted very low activity in protecting LDL from Cu-mediated oxidation
30 and did not display antiradical activities in comparison with the parent, unconjugated aglycone, hydroxytyrosol.

1 Unfortunately, the potential antioxidant activity of the other metabolites, although its presence has been
2 determined in LDL after olive oil consumption [46], has not been addressed so far.

3 **5. Conclusions**

4 The beneficial effects of olive phenolics has been postulated for years but knowledge about the
5 bioavailability and metabolism of some of these compounds is still limited as well as their specific related
6 biological properties. Oleuropein, an important olive phenolic, is extensively metabolized to yield many other
7 metabolites whose specific role in the biological properties attributed to oleuropein is unknown. In our study, the
8 intake of 250 mg of an oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract decreased plasma MDA levels in postmenopausal
9 women which was related to higher plasma levels of metabolites derived from oleuropein. Our results provide
10 preliminary evidence suggesting that in future this oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract could exert benefits against
11 oxidative stress-related processes such as osteoporosis in postmenopausal women. However, the full biological
12 significance of these results and the role of each metabolite in the antioxidant properties of the olive leaf are key
13 issues that are not fully understood so far. Further investigations are warranted to provide insights into the
14 influence of gender, hormonal status and age in olive phenolics metabolism and their effects on the antioxidant
15 status.

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20 Conflict of Interest

21 On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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10 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

11 **Fig. 1** plasma absorption-time profile of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol sulfate, hydroxytyrosol
12 sulfoglucuronide, homovanillic alcohol glucuronide, oleuropein aglycon glucuronide and oleuropein aglycon
13 derivative 1. Data are expressed as mean±SE. AOI, area of intensity. ● premenopausal women; ○
14 postmenopausal women

15 **Fig. 2** urine excretion-time profile of hydroxytyrosol glucuronide, hydroxytyrosol sulfate, hydroxytyrosol
16 sulfoglucuronide, oleuropein aglycon glucuronide and oleuropein aglycon derivative 1, oleuropein aglycon
17 derivative 2 and homovanillic alcohol glucuronide. Data are expressed as mean±SE. AOI, area of intensity. ●
18 premenopausal women; ○ postmenopausal women

19

1 **Table 1.** Identified compounds in the oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract

Peak	Compounds	Retention time (min)	[M-H] ⁻	MS/MS
1	Hydroxytyrosol glucoside	11.65; 11.96	315	153
2	Oleoside	12.09	389	227, 209, 183
3	Luteolin diglucoside	21.99; 24.30	609	447, 285
4	Elenolic acid glucoside	24.618	403	241, 223, 162
5	Dimethyl oleuropein glucoside	24.82	525	481, 389, 363, 347, 319, 209, 195
6	Hydroxy oleuropein glucoside	25.64; 28.16	555	537, 403, 393, 323
7	Rutin	25.82	609	431, 301
8	Luteolin rutinoside	26.15	593	447, 285
9	Verbascoside	26.83; 28.46	623	461, 315
10	Luteolin glucoside	27.02; 30.21	447	285
11	Apigenin rutinoside	28.82	577	269
12	Luteolin rutinoside	29.20	593	285
13	Oleuropein diglucoside	29.50; 30.82	701	539, 377
14	Chrysoeriol glucoside	31.08	461	446, 299
15	Oleuropein glucoside	32.68; 33.84; 34.46	539	437, 403, 377, 275

2

3

4 **Table 2.** Metabolites detected in plasma and urine after the ingestion of 250 mg of oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract.

Main compounds	Retention time (min)	m/z experimental	Score	Error	Molecular Formula	Occurrence
Hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide	4.279	409.0451	95.53	-2.04	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₁₂ S	U, P
Hydroxytyrosol glucuronide	5.251; 5.613	329.0881	98.89	-1.26	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₉	U, P
Hydroxytyrosol sulfate	5.409	233.0129	98.41	-1.79	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₆ S	U, P
Homovanillic alcohol glucuronide	6.200; 7.387	343.1041	97.59	-1.67	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₉	U, P
Oleuropein aglycon derivative 1	12.810; 13.013	571.16.75	99.23	-1.05	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₁₅	U, P
Oleuropein aglycon derivative 2	12.889; 13.228; 13.431	555.1725	99.33	-0.95	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₁₄	U, P*
Oleuropein aglycon glucuronide	14.313;14.460	553.1574	91.23	-2.41	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ O ₁₄	U, P
Oleuropein sulfate	14.923	457.0819	96.22	-2.30	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₁₁ S	U, P*
Tyrosol glucuronide	5.217	313.0939	95.52	-3.11	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₈	U*, P*
Homovanillic alcohol sulfate	6.234	247.0288	95.95	-3.05	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₆ S	U*
Elenolic acid glucuronide	8.019	417.1046	84.8	-0.85	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₁₂	U*
Elenolic acid	10.934	241.0722	98.03	-2.01	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₆	U*
Hydroxytyrosol-acetate glucuronide	11.465	371.0990	80.91	-2.20	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₁₀	U*, P*
Luteolin glucuronide	14.170	461.0707	87.69	3.00	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	P*
Luteolin	15.006	285.0389	85.76	5.83	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	P*

5 U: urine; P: plasma; *compounds present at trace level

6 **Table 3.** Plasma pharmacokinetic parameters of metabolites derived from oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract

Metabolite		Tmax (h)	Cmax ^a	Tlast (h)	AUCall ^b	AUC _∞ ^b	MRTlast (h)	MRT _∞ (h)	T _{1/2} (h)
Hydroxytyrosol glucuronide	Pre	0.62±0.23	2.18±0.65*	24±0.00	4.76±1.39*	5.12±1.43 [#]	3.77±0.68	5.74±2.86	6.53±4.29
	Post	0.56±0.18	3.27±0.55*	24±0.00	6.05±0.89*	6.27±0.89	3.28±0.51	4.32±0.94	6.52±2.65
Hydroxytyrosol sulfate	Pre	1.00±0.46	94±27*	5.75±1.28*	239±67*	259±66*	2.12±0.29	2.91±0.52	1.73±0.49
	Post	1.44±0.98	128±36*	7.25±1.49*	375±96*	389±94*	2.33±0.36	2.95±0.30	1.87±0.38
Hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide	Pre	1.12±0.35	200±104	9.00 ±2.62	656±265	745±259	2.19±0.34	2.99±0.52	2.36±1.52
	Post	0.94±0.18	162±61	8.25±1.67	533±210	646±217	2.43±0.43	3.08±0.46	3.34±2.65
Oleuropein aglycon glucuronide	Pre	0.81±0.26	455±162*	4.50±0.93*	1315±242*	1365±251*	1.48±0.25	1.88±0.20	1.33±0.22*
	Post	0.56±0.18	835±162*	7.25±1.04*	766±312*	854±301*	1.85±0.42	2.47±0.73	2.01±0.77*
Homovanillic alcohol glucuronide	Pre	1.57±0.98	1509±552	24±0.00	8289±1593	10088±3285	7.19±0.93	12.55±6.00	6.32±6.30
	Post	0.79±0.27	1459±359	24±0.00	8283±2999	9466±3308	7.59±1.18	11.47±3.83	7.03±3.70
Oleuropein aglycon derivative 1	Pre	0.81±0.26	174±84*	5.38±1.60	426±180*	543±109 [#]	2.03±0.62	2.81±0.95	1.55±0.58
	Post	1.06±0.42	363±132*	6.00±1.51	780±363*	886±380	2.11±0.46	3.05±0.74	2.01±0.57

7 Data are expressed as mean±SD except for the T_{1/2} parameter that is expressed as the harmonic mean. ^aCmax is expressed as μM for hydroxytyrosol glucuronide and AOI for the rest
8 of metabolites. ^bAUCall and AUC_∞ are expressed as μM h for hydroxytyrosol and as AOI h for the rest of metabolites. *Significant difference (P<0.05) between premenopausal and
9 postmenopausal women. #Marginal difference (0.1>P>0.05)

10 **Table 4.** Urine pharmacokinetic parameters of metabolites derived from oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract

11

Metabolite		Tlag	TmaxRate	MaxRate	AURCall^a	AURC_∞^a	Amount Recovered	T_{1/2}
		(h)	(h)	(h)			($\sum \mu\text{M} \cdot \text{L}$ or $\sum \text{AOI} \cdot \text{L}$)	(h)
Hydroxytyrosol glucuronide	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	9.70±5.31	36.76±17.03	36.99±16.98	46.60±22.34	3.24±0.60
	Post	0±0	2.00±0.00	7.46±2.76	28.57±7.82	28.83±7.73	36.17±10.43	3.50±0.72
Hydroxytyrosol sulfate	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	3032±970*	20849±2888*	22017±2754*	24231±3626*	4.26±0.68
	Post	0±0	2.50±1.41	1815±395*	14928±4024*	16631±4706*	17265±4292*	5.18±1.51 [#]
Hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	503 ±155*	2710±642*	2832±652*	3269±787*	4.88±1.33
	Post	0±0	2.00±0.00	258±84*	1556±480*	1664±477*	1865±552*	5.30±1.20
Oleuropein aglycon glucuronide	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	873±307	3400±1220	3715±969	4285±1523	2.51±0.94
	Post	0±0	2.00±0.00	828±212*	3333±842	3347±843	4164±1040	2.67±0.53
Homovanillic alcohol glucuronide	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	77±35	317±133	328±129	393±167	1.86±0.52
	Post	0±0	2.00±0.00	59±16	263±56	279±62	322±70	2.20±0.56
Oleuropein aglycon derivative 1 (571)	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	791±300	2966±1162	3253±1008*	3783±1473	3.92±1.39
	Post	0±0	2.00±0.00	548±159 [#]	2149±577 [#]	2174±579*	2717±743 [#]	3.49 ±1.46
Oleuropein aglycon	Pre	0±0	2.00±0.00	1381±441	4422±1409	4967±1158	5802±1846	1.29±0.20*

derivative 2 (555)	Post	0±0	2.00±0.00	1245±371	4013±1216	4630±808	5257±1585	1.58±0.16*
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- 12 Data are expressed as mean±SD except for the $T_{1/2}$ parameter that is expressed as the harmonic mean. ^aAUC_{0-t} and AUC_∞ are expressed as μM h for hydroxytyrosol
 13 and AOI h for the rest of metabolites. *Significant difference (P<0.05) between premenopausal and postmenopausal women. #Marginal difference (0.1>P>0.05)

14 Fig. 1

15 Fig. 2

Supplemental Fig. 1 representative HPLC chromatograms of the oleuropein-rich olive leaf extract used in the present study. (a) 280 nm; (b) 320 nm

Supplemental Table 1. Baseline characteristics of participant women

	Premenopausal women (n=8)	Postmenopausal women (n=8)	P
Subjects characteristics			
Age (years)	21.4±1.9	58.8±5.7	<0.00
Weight (kg)	64.7±9.2	65.2±7.7	NS
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	22.7±3.1	23.8±2.5	NS
Blood Pressure (mm Hg)			
Systolic	118.6±8.4	124±14.6	NS
Diastolic	67.1±4.2	75.38±6.6	0.01
Heart rate (bpm)	68.7±8.7	65.7±5.4	NS
Temperature (°C)	36.9±0.3	36.5±0.3	0.02
Hematocrit (%)	40.0±2.9	40.6±2.9	NS
Serum creatinin (μmol/L)	71.7±7.8	72.5±9.9	NS
AST (U/L)	11.5±3.2	14.4±4.7	NS
ALT (U/L)	16.0±4.0	16.1±3.7	NS

Values are expressed as mean±SD. NS, not significant; AST, aspartate transaminase; ALT, alanine aminotransferase.

Supplemental Table 2. MRM conditions optimized for each compound

Compound	Precursor ion	Fragmentor(V)	Quantifier		Qualifier 1		Qualifier 2	
			Product ion	Collision Energy	Product ion	Collision Energy	Product ion	Collision Energy
Hydroxytyrosol glucuronide	329	90	123	36	113	15	153	20
Hydroxytyrosol sulfate	233	90	123	25	153	15		
Hydroxytyrosol sulfoglucuronide	409	90	233	15	329	15		
Homovanillic alcohol glucuronide	343	90	167	15	137	20		
Oleuropein aglycon glucuronide	553	90	377	15	153	25	241	25
Oleuropein aglycon derivative 1	571	90	395	15	377	20	241	25
Oleuropein aglycon derivative 2	555	90	181	25	175	25	361	15